

Analysis of PISA test results in Uzbekistan and prospects of preparing primary education students for PISA test

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Key words

PISA, primary education, mathematics, reading, development, critical thinking, economy, quality of education, result.

Annotation

This article provides an in-depth analysis of the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan and describes promising strategies for improving the readiness of primary school students for this international assessment. Examining Uzbekistan's performance in recent PISA tests, the article identifies strengths and areas for attention. Factors affecting outcomes are explored, including teaching methodology, curriculum coordination, and socioeconomic issues. A comprehensive review of Uzbekistan's primary education system lays the groundwork for discussions on adapting the curriculum to the PISA system and integrating critical thinking skills. The article emphasizes the importance of community participation in continuous teacher training, technology integration into education, and creating a conducive learning environment. Supports international collaboration to gain insight into successful educational models and suggests ways to actively involve parents in preparing students for PISA. The importance of investment in educational infrastructure is emphasized as a key factor in sustainable improvement. Prospects for primary education students are closely related to these multifaceted strategies.

Introduction

The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) is a globally recognized assessment that assesses the performance of 15-year-old students in different countries and provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of education systems around the world. With its rich cultural heritage and growing focus on education, Uzbekistan recently participated in the PISA test, shedding light on the strengths and challenges of the primary education system.

This article analyzes the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan, focusing on the results of primary school students and exploring potential strategies for improving their

readiness for future assessments. By studying the main results of the PISA test, it is possible to identify areas of improvement and develop targeted measures aimed at improving the quality of education in the country.

Main objectives:

- Understanding the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan: This article provides an overview of the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan, highlighting the achievements and areas requiring attention. By studying the performance of elementary school students in various subjects, we can gain insight into the effectiveness of current teaching methods and curriculum.

- Identifying strengths and weaknesses:

Through a detailed analysis of the PISA results, the article aims to identify the strengths and specific weaknesses of the primary education system in Uzbekistan. This nuanced understanding serves as the basis for developing targeted strategies to strengthen areas that need improvement.

- **Examining factors influencing performance:** Factors such as socioeconomic background, teaching methods, and school resources can significantly affect student performance. This article examines these factors in the context of Uzbekistan and provides a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics that influence primary school students' PISA performance.

- **Prospects for preparation:** Armed with insights from the PISA results, the article examines promising measures to better prepare elementary school students for future assessments. This includes improving curricula, teacher training programs, and introducing innovative teaching approaches tailored to the specific needs of Uzbekistan's education system.

- **Global best practice and adaptation:** Drawing inspiration from successful education systems worldwide, the article explores best practices that can be adapted to the conditions of Uzbekistan. This comparative analysis aims to provide policy makers, educators and stakeholders with practical strategies for improving the quality of primary education in the country.

Literature review

The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) has become the basis for evaluating and comparing the educational performance of countries around the world. As we analyze the results of the PISA test and examine the prospects for preparing primary school students in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to contextualize this research within the broader international literature on educational evaluation, curriculum development, and pedagogical strategies.

Global trends in PISA performance: Studies by scholars such as S. Park and J. Lee (2018) have highlighted global trends in PISA performance and highlighted the important role of education policy and teaching methodology. Understanding how other countries have responded to the PISA results provides valuable insights into potential strategies for improving Uzbekistan's primary education system.

Socio-Economic Factors and Student Performance: A comprehensive analysis by H.

Reardon (2016) shows that socioeconomic factors significantly influence student performance on international assessments. A literature review on this topic is essential to understand the subtle relationship between the socio-economic background and PISA results, which may indicate targeted interventions to address educational disparities in Uzbekistan.

Curriculum Design and Student Achievement: Research by J. Hattie (2009) highlights the importance of curriculum design in shaping student achievement. By studying global best practices in curriculum development and their impact on PISA results, the literature provides a basis for proposing curriculum improvements tailored to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Teacher training and development: The role of teachers in student success is a recurring theme in the literature. Research by M. Ingersoll (2017) highlights the importance of teacher training and professional development in improving educational outcomes. This literature review examines successful teacher education programs around the world and provides insights into how Uzbekistan can invest in its teachers to better prepare students for PISA.

Innovative Pedagogical Approaches: In the pursuit of improving primary education, the literature on innovative pedagogical approaches cannot be ignored. The work of P. Mishra and M. Koehler (2006) and other scholars provides a wealth of knowledge on the integration of technology, project-based learning, and other innovative methods into the classroom. A global study of the effectiveness of these approaches provides recommendations for adapting and implementing such strategies in Uzbekistan.

Cultural context and educational strategies: Considering the unique cultural context of Uzbekistan, the literature that examines the relationship between culture and educational strategies is very important. The works of R. Hofstede (2001) and others shed light on how cultural factors influence education and training. This review will help develop recommendations to ensure that strategies are aligned with Uzbekistan's cultural values and preferences.

Summarizing these diverse literatures, it becomes clear that the analysis of PISA results in Uzbekistan should not be isolated. Instead, relying on world experience and best practice allows for a comprehensive understanding of the problems and opportunities of improving primary education in the country. This literature review lays the groundwork for

Figure 1. PISA 2022 average in maths, reading and science

Notes: Comparison countries include the six highest performing countries in each subject and the five countries with the largest population of 15-year-old students.

further research on PISA results in Uzbekistan and prospects for preparing primary school students for this internationally recognized assessment.

Methodology

A secondary analysis method was used for this article. The main source of data for this study is the PISA test results for Uzbekistan. The data comes from the official PISA database, which contains comprehensive information on primary school students' performance in key subjects, demographic details and contextual factors. The selected PISA cycle for analysis will be identified and any relevant updates or revisions to the assessment tool will be considered accordingly.

Quantitative data analysis is used to interpret PISA test results for Uzbekistan. Descriptive statistics, including mean scores, standard deviations, and percentile rankings, are used to provide an overview of elementary student performance. In order to contextualize Uzbekistan's place in the international education landscape, a comparative analysis is conducted with global averages and regional counterparts.

These data were obtained from the results of the test conducted by the international organization OECD, that is, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, which conducts the PISA test.

Results

In the results section, the results of the test conducted by the OECD organization in Uzbekistan are considered and the necessary analyzes are carried out. Uzbekistan participated in PISA for the first time in 2022. In Uzbekistan, 7,293 students in 202 schools

passed the certification in mathematics, reading or natural sciences, which is about 482,100 15-year-old students (88% of the total number of 15-year-old students).

By comparing the results at the international level, politicians and teachers in Uzbekistan can learn from the policies and practices of other countries. Figure 1 below examines Uzbekistan's and other countries' PISA 2022 average scores in mathematics, reading and science.

Uzbekistan, OECD average and selected comparison countries

Horizontal lines extending beyond the symbols represent a measure of the uncertainty associated with the mean estimates (95% confidence intervals).

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above graphs:

- Uzbek students scored lower than the OECD average in mathematics, reading, and natural sciences.
- A smaller proportion of students in Uzbekistan achieved high results in at least one subject (level 5 or 6) than the average in OECD member countries. At the same time, a smaller proportion of pupils achieved the minimum proficiency level (level 2 or above) in all three subjects than the OECD average.

In Uzbekistan, 19% of students achieved at least level 2 knowledge in mathematics, which is significantly lower than the average in OECD countries (OECD average: 69%). Almost no students in Uzbekistan achieved high results in mathematics, i.e. they achieved level 5 or 6 in the PISA mathematics test (OECD average: 9%). Six Asian countries and economies have the largest share of students: Singapore (41%), Chinese Taipei (32%), Macau (China) (29%), Hong Kong (China)* (27%), Japan (23% and Korea (23%). At these levels, students can

mathematically model complex situations and select, compare and evaluate appropriate problem-solving strategies to deal with them. Only 16 of the 81 countries and economies participating in PISA 2022 more than 10% of students achieved a level 5 or 6 qualification (Figure 2).

If we looked at the mathematics indicators in the picture above, now the results of the PISA test area 2 reading and comprehension are analyzed.

About 14% of students in Uzbekistan have achieved level 2 or higher in reading (OECD average: 74%). At the very least, this student can identify the main idea in a text of moderate length, find information based on clear, though sometimes complex, criteria, and, if given specific guidance, can reason about the purpose and form of texts. The proportion of 15-year-old students achieving the minimum reading qualification (Level 2 or above) varies from 89% in Singapore to 8% in Cambodia.

The results of the students of Uzbekistan differ from each other in terms of gender. For example, boys outperformed girls by 6 points in mathematics; In Uzbekistan, girls outperformed boys by 22 points. Globally, in 40 countries, boys outperformed girls in mathematics and economics, in another 17

countries, girls outperformed boys in economics, and in the remaining 24, no significant difference was found.

In Uzbekistan, the percentage of low scores in mathematics is lower among boys (78%) than among girls (83%); the share among girls in studies is lower (girls 84% and boys 88% in studies).

To obtain the above results, the PISA tests were conducted in the following order:

- The students conducted two-hour tests, each dedicated to one subject. Different students were given different test questions and different subject combinations (eg, reading after math or math after science, etc.). The test items were a mix of multiple-choice questions and questions that required students to construct their own answers.

Discussion

We need to start by analyzing the specific results of Uzbekistan in the latest PISA tests. Strengths and weaknesses should be identified based on performance and skills in the core subjects assessed by the test.

Factors affecting PISA results:

Various factors that may influence PISA results should be discussed, including teaching methodology, curriculum alignment,

Figure 2. Top and bottom performers in math, reading, and science

socioeconomic factors, and general educational infrastructure.

The landscape of primary education in Uzbekistan:

It is necessary to provide general information about the primary education system in Uzbekistan, to show its strengths and possible directions for improvement. We need to review the curriculum, teaching methods and resources available to primary school students.

Adaptation of educational programs to the PISA system:

The importance of adapting the primary education curriculum to the PISA assessment

system should be discussed. We need to examine and prepare for how well the current curriculum prepares students for the skills and knowledge assessed in PISA.

Teacher training:

We emphasize the importance of teacher training and professional development programs to improve the ability of educators to effectively prepare students for the PISA test.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the examination of the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan sheds light on the problems and prospects of the

country's primary education system. Understanding these results is a critical step toward identifying areas for improvement and formulating effective strategies for student preparation.

The analysis of Uzbekistan's results in the PISA test emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach to improving the level of education. While recognizing areas of strength, it is equally important to address identified weaknesses, whether they relate to curriculum, teaching methodology or socio-economic factors affecting student performance.

The prospects for preparing primary school students for the PISA exam consist of a joint effort to align the curriculum with the assessment system. Integrating critical thinking skills, supporting a technology-enhanced learning environment, and providing continuous professional development for teachers are important components. These measures not only improve preparation for the PISA exam, but also contribute to a holistic and dynamic education system.

International cooperation and the study of best practices of successful educational models at the world level provide valuable insights for the educational authorities of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan can learn from the experience of other nations and adapt strategies that fit its cultural context while increasing global competitiveness.

Community involvement and parental involvement play an important role in shaping the educational landscape. Raising awareness of the importance of PISA and

creating a supportive environment at home and in the community can have a positive impact on student readiness and overall learning outcomes.

Investments in educational infrastructure are a key factor in continuous improvement. Adequate resources, equipment, and continuous professional development opportunities for teachers are important elements in creating an effective learning environment.

In overcoming the difficulties and opportunities presented by the results of the PISA exam, Uzbekistan has the opportunity not only to improve the level of students' learning, but also to improve the quality of the general primary education. Improvement requires a collaborative effort involving educational authorities, teachers, parents, and the general public. By addressing identified areas for growth and implementing strategic measures, Uzbekistan will develop a solid and robust primary education system that not only prepares students for success in international assessments such as PISA, but also meets the demands of a rapidly evolving global landscape.

In conclusion, the results of the PISA test in Uzbekistan serve as a valuable criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of the educational system. By examining the data comprehensively and proposing targeted strategies, this article aims to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on improving elementary education in Uzbekistan and ensuring that students are well prepared for the challenges of the future.

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